

A Strategy to Transform the Pedagogical Practice of Teaching Teamwork

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Abstract

Organizations worldwide have begun restructuring work around collaborative systems and teamwork to improve problem-solving, innovation, and adaptability. To enhance knowledge appropriation and the development of teamwork competencies, universities have had to incorporate student-centered learning approaches into their curricula. Thus, reforming the Faculty of Engineering of the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana (PUJ) curriculum introduced project-oriented courses. In particular, the Engineering Project Year 1 course brings together second-semester students from different engineering programs who work in groups on the project. Due to the number of students, the course is organized into ten sections, each led by a professor and a coordinator. The course addresses engineering design based on Design Thinking methodology and subsequently proposes the development of a prototype using Lean Start Up methodologies. This study aims to present a strategy that transforms teachers' understanding of what teaching teamwork entails and what strategies can be implemented to teach it. It is qualitative research using the Critical Research methodology proposed by Skovsmose and Borba (2004). This methodology helps researchers and professors collaborate to investigate the educational practice change process through three analytical situations. The analysis of the initial situation shows that the structure of the course can be perceived as facilitating the development of teamwork skills; there are difficulties in its implementation associated with the dynamics between students and between teacher and student. Additionally, it is found that the dominant pedagogical practice is that of a teacher-centered teaching approach, which does not facilitate the generation of a trusting learning environment, a fundamental element in collaboration. The imagined situation involves a better understanding of the role of teachers in teaching teamwork and sharing good practices to achieve it. Finally, the arranged situation presents the challenges of accompanying teachers transforming their pedagogical practice to generate negotiations through reflective conversations to motivate the change.

Keywords: Teaching teamwork; Teacher professional development; Critical Research; Teacher roles in PBL

1 Introduction

In recent years, organizations worldwide have faced increasingly complex, rapidly evolving, and unpredictable environments. As a result, they have started restructuring their work systems to encourage collaboration and teamwork, aiming to enhance problem-solving, innovation, and adaptability (Kolowsky et Chaw, 2018s). This shift in work dynamics has inevitably affected the skills employers expect from university graduates, emphasizing the need for a broader focus on a teacher-learning process that encompasses not only specific competencies but also general or transversal competencies.

Teamwork competencies have become essential to engineering programs due to the emphasis on collaborative work in organizations (Borrego et al., 2013). This is also because international accreditations like ABET make it mandatory for graduates to have these competencies. Along with problem-solving, critical and reflective thinking, and collaboration skills, universities are now focusing on making students more participative in the search for real solutions through student-centered pedagogical models and active learning (Du *et al.*, 2020). However, this has its own challenges, as teachers must adopt new methodologies that involve different roles for both students and teachers in the teaching-learning process.

The problem-based learning model proposed by Kolmos (2004) explains how not only students and teachers are involved in the teaching-learning process. This model establishes that there must be a concordance between changes in each element of the teaching-learning process. Changes in one element lead to other model elements being restructured to achieve an adequate teaching alignment. Therefore, changes in the competencies to be developed imply that other elements, such as the type of work, resources and physical frameworks, and interactions among students, among others, should be evaluated and aligned to ensure educational quality and teaching alignment (Biggs, 2001).

To foster teamwork competency among engineering students, it is crucial to understand how the elements of the teaching-learning ecosystem and the concept of teamwork are interconnected. According to Roberts et al. (2022), a team is a group of two or more individuals who perform specific functions and interact in an adaptive, interdependent, and dynamic manner toward a shared and valued objective. This definition underscores that teamwork and collaboration are not static but active processes that evolve throughout their life cycle (Bedwell et al., 2012). Facilitating this competence development implies that the curriculum's pedagogical strategies must be aligned. Collaborative Learning (CL) is an educational strategy where learners work together to solve problems, accomplish tasks, or create products. Universities worldwide are increasingly adopting this pedagogical strategy because it helps students develop a range of competencies and because national and international frameworks drive universities to reflect on teaching practices in light of the competencies needed in the workforce.

In line with this, the Faculty of Engineering at the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana (PUJ) has adopted the CDIO (Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate) initiative, which exposes students to real-world problems early in their programs. PUJ's engineering programs have established project-based courses over four years, starting from year one, to help students approach real-life problems. As part of this initiative, all engineering programs at PUJ have introduced project-based courses from year 1 to year 4 to provide students with real-life problem-solving experience. However, despite the availability of a framework for using collaborative learning as a pedagogical strategy consistent with the CDIO model, the curriculum reforms did not include a systematic and continuous teacher training program. Additionally, these courses are challenging for teachers to address since they involve the generation of tools and class dynamics that enable solving real problems, thinking critically, and working collaboratively, which implies a shift related to the teacher's role regarding the interaction with the student and the solution proposed and greater autonomy on the part of the students in terms of exploring the solution. Consequently, ensuring teachers have the tools to shift from traditional to student-centered teaching is impossible.

Regarding the curriculum, the Engineering Project Year 1 course is offered for second-semester Engineering Faculty students. This course introduces students to engineering design processes, emphasizing problem design and problem-solving using Design Thinking tools. Lean start-up methodologies are also taught to help the students develop a prototype. The course problem is related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which aim to raise awareness among students about their context and to identify local and national problems. One of the learning outcomes of this course is to enable students to foster a collaborative work environment.

For this reason, tools from the Scrum methodology have been implemented, such as a project management framework that encourages teams to learn from experiences, self-organize, and reflect on results. The methodology must be applied throughout the development of the course's deliverables. Regarding the logistics, this is an extensive course with around 300 students. The course is divided into smaller units of about 25 students each. Each teacher is responsible for supporting five work groups within each course. About ten teachers are required for this course, eight working part-time. The course coordinator is responsible for aligning the course activities and defining the project topics. The coordinator also organizes general meetings with

experts on the project topics, coordinates the work of the professors, oversees the final student presentations, addresses any concerns raised by the teachers, and ensures that the teachers are aligned with the proposed learning outcomes.

We have faced some implementation difficulties after running a course for six semesters. One of the challenges is that most professors teaching the course are part-time. Therefore, we have formed two research questions to address the situation: RQ1. Considering the context conditions mentioned above, what are the primary obstacles to creating a collaborative environment for the Year 1 project of the PUJ engineering programs? RQ2. How can the teaching practices of the PUJ professors be transformed to promote the development of teamwork competencies in this course?

2 Methodology

This qualitative study is framed in Critical Research (Skovsmose & Borba, 2004). Critical research proposes developing participatory and collaborative research between teachers and researchers to generate transformations in classroom problems, evidencing the interaction between theoretical perspectives and methodologies present when conducting educational research. Skovsmose and Borba state that to generate changes, it is necessary to break with the model of investigating what is and what has happened to investigate what would be possible. Consequently, they suggest that transformation occurs by traversing a triangle between three analytical situations and the relationships between them. In the initial situation, possibilities for transformation are identified by systematically analyzing what happens in the classroom and the learning environment. Based on this analysis, an imagined situation is proposed, which represents the vision of the possibilities and alternatives for change to address what was identified in the initial situation. However, when implementing the proposals for change in the imagined situation, limitations associated with resources and implementation barriers emerge because conditions must permanently restrict the possibilities of realizing everything we imagine. From this disparity emerges the fixed situation as a realistic vision of the imagined situation. Central to critical research are the relationships between situations. These situations represent the negotiation between actors to achieve a specific outcome. They are the conscience of participatory actions and the only way to mobilize someone.

The research team is formed by a doctoral student who is a civil engineer, a lecturer in the course Engineering Project Year 1, and her thesis director, a physicist with a PhD in innovative curricula in science and technology in higher education. They collaborated with three professors (P1, P2, P3) who agreed to participate in the project. They are part-time lecturers with about ten years of experience as part-time lecturers at PUJ and with the course coordinator [P4].

Initial interviews were conducted to understand the professors' perspectives before interventions, and the classes of the same professors were observed during the semester. After interventions, interviews were carried out. The information was processed and categorized according to the theories of constructive alignment (Biggs, 2001) and the collaborative learning theory proposed by Johnson and Johnson (2013).

The information was transcribed and analyzed in the following way: To approach the initial situation, we aimed to understand the conceptions of the Year 1 project course teachers about teamwork and the pedagogical strategy they use in the course. We used pedagogical imagination to propose the imagined situation based on recognizing successful practices and theoretical elements such as transformative learning and constructive alignment. Finally, a practical organization is required to implement what is proposed, giving rise to the arranged situation. When implementing the imagined situation, a practical organization must be carried out, which consists of validating what is possible versus what is imagined.

3 Results

3.1 Initial situation

The teaching approaches vary across classes. P1 and P2 classes typically involve a lecture for half of the session, followed by project implementation based on initial class observations. In contrast, P3 classes feature more active dynamics, with theory quickly followed by practical application. The master class presents Engineering design concepts and examples from the teacher's professional experience, resulting in limited student participation, mainly through sporadic responses to rhetorical questions. In practical sessions, the teacher rotates among groups, addressing doubts, approving work, and providing specific instructions for improvement. This pattern repeats across all three classes, with teachers actively shaping students' work during group interactions.

In team dynamics [P1, P2, P3], the teacher assumes a central role in guiding students' development of teamwork competencies and managing their learning processes. The teacher mediates group conflicts, often engaging in negotiations and compromises with students to resolve issues. Students typically present problems and await the teacher's intervention to resolve them. While each teacher exhibits varying degrees of control over team dynamics, discussions regarding team performance and management primarily flow from teacher to student. These discussions typically arise at three junctures: when groups bring team conflicts to the teacher's attention, when the teacher identifies subpar product quality, or when student attendance issues arise and become evident to the teacher. However, it is uncommon for teachers to actively foster reflective spaces for students to contemplate teamwork dynamics despite the prevalence of conflicts within teams.

The coordination has established evaluation tools to assess team performance, which are utilized by teachers based on their individual understanding and implementation. For instance, in P2 classes, team-building activities are notably absent, whereas P1 classes adhere closely to coordination directives. In P3 classes, peer evaluations are conducted in real-time, whereas in P2, the evaluation and co-evaluation survey activity is relegated to outside class time due to concerns over content coverage.

The course coordinator emphasizes that each professor has autonomy in course management but encourages dialogue at the semester's end to review course experiences [IP4]. During collective meetings with all professors, the focus is often on product quality, yet mid-semester meetings sometimes reveal statements from professors regarding group performance and student conflicts. In this regard, the coordinator states, "...there are teachers with groups of students that separate more. We need training on how to manage conflicts with students, but it is also true that we do not know how to manage conflict among ourselves. So, it is difficult to expect teachers to support students in doing so" [P4].

Teachers generally understand the importance of teamwork but often struggle with their role in developing this competency. The course is structured around projects, and some Scrum tools are used to help students manage their teams and apparently achieve project objectives without much intervention from the teacher. However, few tools available allow for reflection on teamwork performance, which means there is no intentional focus on developing this competence. As a result, teachers may assume a range of positions, from passive observers to overly controlling, and students may not receive the scaffold necessary to develop their teamwork competencies. Recurrently, in interviews, teachers referred to their approach to teaching, where they are responsible for approving or rejecting students' work. Some teachers focus more on the outcome of the work, while others are more involved in managing the deliverable process. For example, P1 said, "I give instructions and then provide feedback on the final result." P2 said, "I set the conditions for the students to work, but I do not get involved in the process."

On the other hand, P3 emphasized the need for control in managing students' work, saying, "I think all teachers should handle the same scheme of managing the work of the groups. We should all ask them for memos of their meetings and check whether they are fulfilling their responsibilities." Overall, it is clear that teachers have different approaches to managing their students' work, with some focusing on the final result and others on team management regarding the deliverable process.

In addition, teachers have reported difficulties in establishing strategies for developing teamwork competencies during group professor meetings and individual interviews. As observed in the group meetings held twice a semester, teachers usually indicate that they have difficulties addressing the problems students face in their work groups. The professors refer to two situations that make teamwork difficult: students who are part of a group that does not get involved in the work of the "free riders" team and groups of students who approach the problems dealt with during the semester superficially. The action in front of these two situations varies according to how each teacher approaches the situation. In cases where the teacher cannot handle the situation, the program coordinator ends up intervening in the students who are not engaged [P4]. "Refer to my office the students who have problems that I talk to them to get them "aligned".". Generally, teachers express frustration with the student's motivation with the project and the management of conflictive teams: "There are irresponsible students who do not want to work with the project", "there are irresponsible students who do not want to work," or "I scare them so that they work well as a team" [P1]. In this type of statement, the limitations regarding the possibilities of action to mobilize the teams from a constructive point of view are evident.

Despite these concerns, teachers highly recognize the importance of developing this teamwork competency in students: "This competency is important for the working world but especially for engineering because this is developed in multidisciplinary groups." [P3]. Likewise, the teachers' conception of what teamwork means has several elements framed within the theories of teamwork conception that involve aspects of communication, coordination, individual and group responsibility for the task, and recognition of the objective, among others. In the conceptualization given by the teachers, there is little reference to the description of the type of interactions expected to occur during the evolution of the teams in the project. The underlying question is how the teacher conceives the teaching-learning process. The collection of evidence allows for visualizing an understanding of teaching in which the teacher is the one who delivers knowledge, and the student uses it under the teacher's supervision. For example, how does the teacher conceive the teaching-learning process?

In conclusion, the description of the initial situation allows evidence of two fundamental aspects that condition the development of teamwork competencies: first, the teacher's conception of the teaching-learning process and, within this framework, the transformative learning for the gain of autonomy by the student, and second, the formative intention of the activities developed in class and their alignment with the learning outcomes and specifically with the teamwork competency.

3.2 Imagined situation and pedagogical imagination

The imagined situation considers the solution to the challenges posed in the initial situation. On the one hand, it is expected that the teacher can generate a collaborative environment in the classroom, where the student experiences the design of a problem and its solution. In this process, the teacher must have the tools to accompany what emerges from the students' search, both related to the project's conceptualization and the elements of teamwork that are expected to be articulated. To this end, the teacher must question his role in the learning process from a vision centered on the student as the leading actor in the learning process and understand how the design thinking scheme of the course and the instruments used in class can enhance the development of teamwork competence.

Learning understood from the sociocultural view (Vygotsky, 1978) is a complex process product of the activity, context, and culture where it is developed and used. In this approach, the role of the teacher changes from one that presents information to one that designs and facilitates processes and designs learning environments that increase student engagement. The incorporation of projects in the curriculum is intended to bring students closer to complex problems, where they participate and approach the solution, involving not only knowledge but also their identity, meanings, and past experiences, having to contrast their frames of reference with other individuals and environments in the learning process. For this to happen, the teacher must shed his or her role of authority in class and empower students as actors in their own learning process. In discussions with the course coordination, observation and construction with teachers are proposed to generate tools and strategies that allow the mobilization of teachers towards the conceptualization of teamwork and its implementation in the classroom so that the teacher is reflective concerning how each of the course tools (Scrum, peer, and self-assessment, team contract, among others) can be used in the development of teamwork competence, taking into account the formative intentionality when using each tool.

With the observed teachers, it is agreed to reflect on what is being implemented in the classroom, in light of the conception of learning from the sociocultural vision of Vygotsky (1978), constructive alignment in teaching (Biggs, 2001) and cooperative learning (Jhonson & Jhonson, 2013). Intervention strategies are focused on accompanying teachers who have been observed. A reflective scheme is established and incorporated in classes that are accompanied every week or two. Teachers P1 and P2 begin to question themselves about the quality of classroom teaching based on questions asked at the end of each class session about their approach to learning. The questions aim to understand the teacher's vision of what is observed as teaching practice in the classroom and are generally associated with the teacher's formative intention with the development of the activities proposed for the class and the degree to which he/she perceives that he/she achieves that the students are learning. The initial questioning carried out in the interviews, and as a conclusion of the initial observations, presents us with a first moment where teachers express doubts about whether they are developing the competence in the students: "I thought I was developing the competence of working in teams, but now I wonder if the students do it and how they do it" [P2]. These types of dilemmas were observed in the case of teachers P1 and P2.

Regarding teacher P3, there were no significant inquiries about pedagogical practices or classroom change during the reflective conversations at the end of class. When asked about teaching-learning theories, teacher P3's concepts aligned with the theory: "Students are responsible for their learning, and my role is to motivate reflection in the teams". However, there were differences between the class dynamics and the theory. These differences were observed in class observations. During the presentation of a workgroup with difficulties in their organization as a team, the P3 teacher comments on the quality of the work done and the difficulties they are having as a team and invites them to reflect. Subsequently, he conducts a conversation with the work group where, after inquiring about how they are working, he tells them that they should present actions for improvement. When teacher P3 was asked about his formative intention aligned with the way of proceeding, no answers were found that would allow the initiation of more reflective questions. Interventions with this type of teacher may require more time due to the need to discuss particular topics and the limited availability of part-time teachers, so it was decided not to continue with the process of accompaniment with this teacher.

The initial observation exercise that was carried out with teachers P1 and P2 is just the starting point to support teachers in their transformation. The goal of the exercise is to encourage reflection that will lead to changes in the classroom, promoting collaborative learning through using explicit tools that facilitate teamwork. Together, teachers and students create a shared understanding of teamwork. Figure 1 shows how the course tools can support creating effective teams. The structure of the intervention is related to the dynamics of the classes. In

the initial phase of the course, the primary focus is on fostering trust. In the second stage, the focus shifts to developing mechanisms for coordination and control. In the third stage, the emphasis is on conflict management. These stages are developed this way due to the students' needs throughout the course.

Figure 1. Classroom intervention strategies concerning the conceptualization of teamwork.

Two strategies have been established with the course coordinator: firstly, the training of all teachers to motivate the development of collaborative work competence among first-year engineering students. This involves transforming teaching practices to promote cooperation in the classroom and providing reflective support to teachers. Secondly, the professors will be accompanied throughout the semester to reflect on the teaching-learning process under a sociocultural vision and to assist in implementing the tools developed to generate student reflections on teamwork. In addition to training, the coordination seeks to schedule spaces to encourage the participation of teachers in reflection and the use of tools to develop teamwork competence. The intervention scheme of accompaniment agreed with the teachers for reflection is proposed according to Kolb's (1984) learning model, where the learning cycle has four stages: concrete experience, reflective observation, practical conceptualization, and active experimentation.

3.3 Arranged situation

This situation is based on a set of negotiations that consist of systematically addressing with teachers the strategies for implementing the tools that can be used to develop teamwork skills in the classroom. The strategy of using Scrum tools for reflection and the need for the evaluation to incorporate more elements of teamwork are presented to the course coordinator, who recognizes the importance of implementing the strategy.

At the beginning meeting of the semester, the plan for the use of the tools that the course provides for the development of reflections in students is presented. This meeting was intended to be aligned with the teacher training planned for the beginning of the semester. However, training does not take place until the middle of the semester because most of the professors are part-time, and there are crossovers regarding the availability of schedules. The training occurs in the middle of the semester, with five-course teachers and the coordinator. This presents a limitation in the ability to incorporate a new vision strategically in the semester's courses due to the limited number of attendees and the time at which it is carried out. Even though it was impossible to align this training with the accompaniment of teachers due to the disparity of the moments of conceptualization, this affected the vision of the teachers who attended. The professors expressed a new vision about their role in developing competence: "On the training day, I learned about the importance of developing teamwork competence. The course content is very focused on developing the design thinking methodology, and for me, the emphasis on teamwork was secondary. I used to see it as a marginal topic, and only on the training day carried out I recognized it was important". These kinds of comments show that the trainings facilitate the reflection of these issues among the teaching staff, which can be potentiated to promote the

transformations of teachers concerning their pedagogical practices and reflective spaces in developing transversal competencies. Agreeing on spaces for intervention with the group of teachers becomes complex due to the difficulty that arises when coordinating meetings outside the workspaces.

The accompaniment scheme was carried out with P1 and P2 teachers following the Kolb learning cycle (1984). An example is the situation observed concerning incorporating the reflection strategy into the work carried out. After the first deliverable, P1 plans to reflect on the team's performance. The concrete experience, in this case, is based on the teacher's previous experience concerning applying the teamwork tools. In the planning conversation, the teacher says: "We are going to reflect on the work, but survey and reflection must be done as homework to save time in class." Reflective observation is generated by posing questions to know the intention and developing some activities during class. Abstract conceptualization is based on the answers given by the teacher, thus reinforcing the theory of constructive alignment (Biggs, 2001). Finally, in the moment of active experimentation, P1 expresses its intention to apply the tools in class: it applies the self-evaluation and co-evaluation tools. It shows the results in groups, delivers feedback on the work done, and then generates a space where the students discuss the results obtained in the partial evaluation and how they work as a team. As a result of this exercise, the contract agreement is modified according to group reflection. The teacher rotates through all the groups to listen to the reflections they make as a group. The groups actively discuss based on the inputs provided by the teacher. At the end of the class, there is a dialogue with the teacher about what was observed in the groups. After, some reflective questions are done. P1 reflects: "It was exciting to hear them talk. Some groups continue to have problems, but I think it is a moment where they can start discussing with their peers with objective tools... I think the results of this exercise differ from those they have when they do their homework at home. These are reflections that can motivate real changes in the team."

3.4 Exploratory reasoning

The situations presented present the need to transform the teacher's teaching practices, which should lead to the generation of collaborative environments in the classroom with greater student participation. This implies that teachers must be aware of the transformation processes beyond implementing tools in the classroom. From Merizow's perspective of transformative learning (1997), transformation implies a change that involves integrating what has been learned into the daily routine of teaching practice. This is one of the main challenges in transformation because it implies the teacher's agency to reflect on their practice and act towards incorporating strategies that begin to be part of their identity. This shift is evident in the narrative of the P1 teacher, who considered the reflection of teamwork as a secondary component of his teaching. However, after training and hands-on experience, your perspective changes radically. P1 perceives the importance of actively engaging students in reflecting on their teamwork, recognizing that these reflections can motivate significant changes in team behavior. This change in the perception and pedagogical practice of the P1 teacher reflects a process of educational transformation according to Mezirow's theory. From the perspective of developing teamwork competencies, the P1 teacher demonstrates a progression in his ability to facilitate collaborative learning and reflection among his students. Initially, I plan to have students reflect outside the classroom to save time. However, as the process progresses and she actively experiments with applying tools such as self-assessment and in-class feedback, she recognizes the value of taking time in the classroom for students to reflect and discuss together. This change in the P1 practice indicates progress towards actively promoting collaborative learning and the development of teamwork competencies in students. Likewise, in the example, P1 proposes a change towards incorporating the tools as an element that promotes student reflection from a disciplinary perspective and the way interactions occur in the classroom.

Finally, although it is not possible to evidence the pedagogical transformation of the rest of the group of teachers, it is observed that it is possible to generate a disorienting dilemma based on training that leads to

the permanent reflection of the teacher. Teachers are willing to reflect on what happens in the classroom because they understand their responsibility to train professionals. According to the information collected, there are two barriers in the process of implementing changes in the classroom: on the one hand, the change in the level of authority in the class, granting power of action to the student, and on the other hand, the lack of conceptualization regarding the teaching of competencies such as teamwork.

4 Conclusions

The pedagogical transformation for the development of teamwork competencies implies a conceptualization of collaborative learning by teams, where the student is the one who takes action in their learning process. Part-time teachers say they do not have time to implement substantial changes in their subjects. However, by addressing situations reflectively, they naturally begin to change their teaching practice. This ends up being an example replicable to their own practice, where it is observed that there is beginning to be a transition towards practices that are less focused on the teacher.

Several tools can be used in the course with a formative intention associated with developing teamwork. How to articulate them to develop competencies depends on the teacher's vision of teaching, which can take them as tools that the student must learn to use or tools that allow team management as a final goal.

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